

CHARACTERIZATION OF IMPACT DAMAGE IN CFRPS USING A SCANNING ACOUSTIC MICROSCOPE

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SUMMARY: This paper describes the quantitative technique using scanning acoustic microscopy (SAM) for characterizing the low energy impact delamination at individual laminar interfaces of carbon fibre/modified bismaleimide laminated composites. Accurate information on the damaged states, such as size and shape of delaminations through-the-thickness distribution, can be obtained using three kinds of ultrasonic techniques in reflection mode, namely ply-by-ply scanning, time-of-flight and B-scan analysis. Good correlation is found between the results obtained from fractography and SAM experiments. As a rapid, non-destructive inspection tool, SAM is also a powerful technique to characterize the micro-deformation and damage propagation mechanisms in the compression after impact (CAI) test specimens.

KEYWORDS: scanning acoustic microscopy (SAM), low-velocity impact, delamination, compression after impact (CAI), time-of-flight analysis

INTRODUCTION

During recent years the use of fiber reinforced laminated composites for primary and secondary aircraft structures has rapidly increased, mainly due to the need for reduced weight. One of the major concerns for a designer is the exact knowledge of the effect of impact damage on residual structural performance of these materials because the impact damage considerably reduces the stiffness and strength, particularly under compression [1]. However, the characterization of the damage tolerance is complicated by the fact that delaminations and cracks are often not on the impacted surface. Due to the lack of damage assessment capability and analytical models which can accurately predict the impact damage in laminated composites [2], composite parts are generally restricted to load or strain levels far below their potential.

Therefore, it is apparent that a reliable nondestructive evaluation (NDE) technique for assessing impact damage in composite structures is needed. X-ray radiography is often used to detect transverse cracking [3]. Conventional ultrasonic techniques are commonly used for characterization of delaminations with satisfactory results, but they often fail to detect micro-cracks and multiply-delaminations. Delamination is one of the most critical damage modes in laminated composites subjected to local bending and/or low-velocity impact [4].

An accurate description of delaminations and matrix cracking through the thickness is needed for better understanding of the damage process and their consequences. However, few ultrasonic methods have been reported on these subjects in the current literature [5]. Although some advanced ultrasonic set-ups can provide useful data, very complicated and expensive features such as multiple gates, multiple channels, multiple receivers, are necessary. They often fail to give good damage evaluations because of three dimensional images which are not appropriated [6]. As a consequence, current understanding of damage growth mechanisms due to impact is still limited.

The main purpose of the present study is to evaluate the multi-ply delaminations size and through-the-thickness damage distribution using advanced digital scanning acoustic microscopy (SAM). The details of three techniques, which are used to measure the ply-by-ply delamination shape, size and their distributions through the specimen thickness, are described. They are the C-scan based on the amplitude measurement in a thin time gate automatically shifted at each point along the time axis to cover the entire thickness of specimen; the time-of-flight (TOF) analysis, and the conventional B-scan imaging technique. Fractographic evaluation is also used to compare with the SAM results. Furthermore, the foregoing techniques are also used to study the damage propagation in composites containing different matrix materials.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The composite laminates studied were fabricated from Toray T300 carbon fibers and two different grades of modified bismaleimide (MBMI) : 2MBMI and 4MBMI which represent those designed for high temperature tolerance and low viscosity, respectively. The MBMI resins contained different amounts of polyethersulfone (PES) particles according to the supplier, Beijing Aeronautical Manufacturing Technology Research Institute (BAMTRI), China [8]. All laminate panels were made by hand lay-up of 16 layer prepregs with a lay-up sequence of $[(45/0/-45/90)_2]_s$. The nominal fiber volume fraction was 60%, and the thickness of the plate was 2.0 mm.

All impact tests were performed at room temperature with 100 mm × 100 mm square specimens on an instrumental impact tester, Dynatub 8250 Impact Test Machine. An impactor of weight 2.42 kg and with a hemispherical nose of 25.4 mm in diameter was impacted onto the centre of specimen whose edges were clamped between two circular rings. An energy of 5.3 J was applied to produce damage which could be only barely visible on the impacted surface. The load-displacement records were obtained directly from the data acquisition system.

The CAI tests were conducted on a Sintech 10/D Minnesota Testing Systems (MTS) using a Boeing Compression After Impact Test Fixture (BSS 7260).

The impact damage was evaluated by means of an advanced scanning acoustic microscope (SAM), Sonix Micro-Scan System. A focused acoustic beam was used to scan over the plane of the damaged laminate in a gated pulse-echo mode. The transducer with a 15 MHz probe was mounted on computer-controlled bridges, allowing a complete scan of test samples. Distilled water was used as the coupling medium between the transducer and test specimen. Measurements were made on a 90 mm × 90 mm area using a 250 × 250 point sampling grid which were processed using a software on a personal computer. Reflectograms of A-scan were recorded to show the amplitude/time response obtained on an undamaged area and areas

having delaminations at different interfaces. The amplitude of the echo reflected by a delamination is measured by placing the test gate on the representative region of the thickness of the structure to be tested, between the front surface echo and the back surface echo.

In addition to the ply-by-ply C-scan analysis which generates the images of gross damage through the whole laminate thickness, the time-of-flight (TOF) techniques were also applied to obtain the information about damage on individual plies. Because the flaw signals appeared in the gate placed on the time axis between the upper and lower sides of the specimen, quantitative calibration units could be performed in absolute to correlate the gray level with the depth of delaminations in the specimen. Having obtained the C-scan images, the cursor controlled x-y positions and amplitude-depth data were recorded.

After the SAM characterization, the specimen was examined destructively by cutting through the thickness and photographed using an optical stereo microscope to compare the damage detected by this method with that detected ultrasonically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ultrasonic Pulse-Echo Scanning of the Impacted Composite Plates

Fig. 1 shows the whole accumulated damage area obtained from the C-scan image. The level of gray colour indicates the depth of the layer containing damages from the front surface. The total damage is in the form of a circle confirming the earlier finding [4] for a laminate composite with a similar lay-up sequence. Fig. 2(a) and (b) exhibit delaminations on the top eight layers of the laminate which were obtained from the ply-by-ply C-scan technique and the time-of-flight analysis, respectively. The ply-by-ply C-scanning allows imaging of damages accumulated ply-by-ply toward the bottom layer. Because of the duration of the ultrasonic echo, the measurements made in a given window for delamination on a layer may have also been influenced by delaminations above it. Even so, the distribution of delamination through-the-thickness can be evaluated. In the time of flight analysis, clearer individual delamination shape and through-the-thickness damage distribution can be obtained by controlling the cursor' gray level.

Fig. 1: A pulse-echo ultrasonic C-scan image of the impacted composite plate. The horizontal line, crossing delaminations in the fourth, fifth, sixth and seventh interface.

Table 1: The depth and size of delamination measured by time of flight analysis and fractography.

Fig. 2: The delamination patterns obtained from the front (impacted) surface up to the eighth ply (see table 1) by (a) ply-by-ply C-scanning, (b) time-of-flight analysis. (c) Schematic showing the distribution of delamination through-the-thickness of composite.

The delamination patterns on the eight layers of the laminate close to the bottom, which cannot be detected from front side due to shielding effect [7], were also produced in a similar way. As a consequence, an illustration of all the delaminations in an impacted composite plate is given in Fig. 2(c). It is noted that the delamination in a layer is “peanut shaped” with its major axis oriented in the direction of fiber of the lower ply and does not occur between two layers with the same orientation.

The quantitative results obtained for the same laminate are summarized in Table 1. The depths of delamination on individual plies were calculated by:

$$\text{Depth} = [\text{Plate thickness} / \text{Time of flight for plate}] \times \text{Time of flight for delamination.} \quad (1)$$

The depths of damage calculated in this way are in good agreement with those obtained from cross-sectional fractography. It is worth noting that all delamination propagated along the laminar interfaces owing to the inherent weakness of the interface. The sizes of delamination on each layer are also included in Table 1.

Fig. 3: The 3-D profile of time of flight image showing the delamination on the third interlayer; gray levels indicate the depth of delamination from the front surface.

Fig.4: Cross-sectional view of delaminations in the fourth, fifth, sixth and seventh interface by (a) B-scan image, and (b) fractography along the line shown in Fig.1.

Furthermore, Fig. 3 shows a detailed three-dimensional time-of-flight image which suggests that the delamination on an interlaminar plane is not smooth, but microscopically rough, reflecting the toughness and impact resistance of the composite.

Fractography

To verify the above SAM result, the laminate whose damages are shown in Fig.1 was cut along the line 4-7. The polished cross-section was examined using an optical stereo microscope to compare the damage detected by B-scan, as shown in Fig. 4. The results clearly indicate that the number and through-the-thickness distribution of the delaminations measured by the two methods agree excellently.

Comparison of Damage Patterns of T300-2MBMI with that of T300-4MBMI

Because the T300-4MBMI system contained more thermoplastic particles, it has lower viscosity, significantly higher impact resistance and damage tolerance than the T300-2MBMI system at room temperature. Comparison of the SAM results showed considerable differences in the delamination size and the distribution through the specimen thickness: (i) As shown in Fig. 5, the relatively tougher T300-4MBMI composite has a smaller

damage area, with damage occurring on fewer layers than the brittle system (T300-2MBMI). (ii) The size of delamination on individual interface gradually increased though the thickness for the brittle system, while it decreases for tougher system (see Fig.5(b) and (c)). (iii) The most striking characteristic of the T300-4MBMI composite was that the front surface swelled after impact, an indication of plastic deformation being an important impact energy absorbing mechanism for this system at room temperature.

Fig. 5: Comparison of damage patterns of T300-2MBMI (left) and T300-4MBMI (right) composites by (a) C-scan images, (b) B-scan images (cross-section view along the lines in (a)) and (c) time of flight analysis (showing damage distribution through-the-thickness).

Damage Patterns of CAI Plate

When loaded in compression, impact damaged laminates experience significant strength reductions, due mostly to local instabilities [9]. Fig. 6 illustrated the C-scan images of the CAI test specimen. The laminate failed by buckling with significant delamination growth in the transverse direction. It suggests that buckling took place under compression from the impact damage present in the top several layers. The cracks extended along approximately 45° direction of compression, causing catastrophic fracture. The delamination extended completely across the specimen width but extended only a short distance in the loading direction. On the other hand, the delamination present on the other layers were not seriously affected by the CAI test.

Because the ability to predict the residual strength of a damaged structure is of major importance for an effective damage tolerant design, the SAM techniques described above can provide useful information for developing a quantitative analytical model.

Fig. 6: C-scan images of the CAI plate showing the overall (a) and individual (b) delamination distribution through-the-thickness.

CONCLUSIONS

Accurate information on the damage states, such as three dimensional shape, size and distribution of multi-layer delaminations, is generated from the study of three different ultrasonic techniques based on SAM experiments. Excellent correlation is observed between the results obtained from these techniques and fractography.

There are considerable differences between CFRPs containing two different BMI matrix materials in terms of delamination size and distribution through the specimen thickness, which in turn reflect different micro-deformation and damage mechanisms.

As a rapid, non-destructive inspection tool, SAM is a powerful technique to characterize the delaminations and their propagation in CAI test specimens.

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